

Medium Dependence of Acid-Catalyzed Formamide Hydrolysis

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Manuscript received 27 October 1979, accepted 9 April 1980

The acid hydrolysis of formamide was carried out in aqueous-, methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, isopropanol, tert-butanol and ethylene glycol.

The rate of the reaction was found to increase in aqueous-, methanol and ethylene glycol and to decrease continuously in aqueous isopropanol while minima were observed in the other solvents. This behaviour was interpreted on the basis of the solvent structure and the role of water in the mechanism of the reaction.

FROM the theoretical point of view, it is well known that, the solvation process gives the system a state of stability as a result of the energy lost in the electrostatic work done due to this process. It is also a known fact that equilibria will shift towards more polar products in more polar solvents.

These rational points of view made Hughes and Ingold¹ to assume that the energy change will dominate the rate change, where the more polar solvent will enhance or retard the reaction depending on whether the transition state is more or less polar than the initial state.

In the literature, there are data which support² this postulate; also there are other data which do not³ as found in the present investigation.

It is thus pertinent to enlarge the scope of the traditional treatment of the medium effect, specially the electrostatic properties of the medium, and invoke other factors which seem to give reasonable interpretation of these anomalous data.

Experimental

Purification of solvents and Formamide: The solvents and formamide which have been used in this work were of the best grade available from B.D.H.; further purification for each solvent and formamide were carried out as reported⁴. Solvent mixtures were usually made up by weight, and the ratio of the formamide : hydrochloric acid was 1 : 1 where the concentration of each reactant was 0.1 M.

The kinetic technique (ion exchange) has been described⁵, and second order kinetic was observed for at least 80% reaction. The reaction was thermostated at $25^{\circ} \pm 0.02^{\circ}$. Complete hydrolysis was assured by the coincidence of the theoretical and the experimental values.

Results and Discussion

The rate of the acid hydrolysis of formamide was measured in methanol-, ethanol-, *n*-propanol, isopropanol, tert-butanol, and ethylene glycol-water mixtures in the range from 0.0% to almost 90% by weight organic solvent. The hydrolysis was found to follow a second order kinetic rate equation. A typical example of the acid hydrolysis of formamide in ethanol-water mixtures is shown in Fig. 1. From such plots, extrapolated values for the specific rate constant were obtained and assembled in Table 1, and represented graphically in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Second order plots at 25° in ethanol-water mixtures.

 Fig. 2. Variation of k_2 with wt% alcohol.

 TABLE I—RATE CONSTANTS ($\ln \text{l-mole}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$) FOR THE ACID HYDROLYSIS OF FORMAMIDE IN PRESENCE OF ALCOHOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 25°C

Solvent wt%	$10^4 k_2$					
	methanol	ethanol	n-propanol	isopropanol	t-butanol	ethylene glycol
0	1.765	1.765	1.765	1.765	1.765	1.765
5	1.975	1.638	1.580	1.520	1.628	1.790
10	2.185	1.522	1.415	1.330	1.490	1.815
15	2.400	1.414	1.280	1.190	1.350	1.843
20	2.620	1.321	1.180	1.070	1.211	1.873
25	2.830	1.242	1.105	0.990	1.070	1.905
30	3.042	1.174	1.055	0.917	0.929	1.938
35	3.255	1.122	1.026	0.848	0.789	1.972
40	3.475	1.087	1.026	0.790	0.685	2.007
45	3.690	1.060	1.035	0.742	0.700	2.043
50	3.900	1.044	1.055	0.700	0.778	2.082
55	4.110	1.045	1.092	0.655	0.827	2.125
60	4.330	1.055	1.160	0.615	0.921	2.172
65	4.550	1.074	1.231	0.575	0.995	2.225
70	4.760	1.102	1.305	0.538	1.068	2.283
75	4.985	1.136	1.383	0.510	1.142	2.343
80	5.200	1.176	1.463	0.480	1.215	2.400
85	5.410	1.218	1.545	0.460	1.290	2.465
90	5.640	1.262	1.640	0.440	1.362	2.525

The effect of the dielectric constant: According to the Hughes and Ingold theory¹, the rate of the reaction between an ion and a dipolar molecule,

must increase as the polarity of the solvent decreases due to the dispersal of the charge on the activated complex. Aqueous, methanol and ethylene-glycol show perfect agreement with such theory, but the reaction in the other solvents shows anomalous results as shown in Fig. 3.

 Fig. 3. Influence of dielectric constant on k_2 in *n*-propanol-water mixtures.

To interpret these anomalous data we have to take into consideration two factors: (a) the role of water in the mechanism of the reaction, and (b) the change in the structure of water in the mixed solvent which may take place as the composition changes.

The role of water in the mechanism: Bunnett⁶, developed an approach which was used as a criterion of mechanism based on detailed analysis of results for many reactions. The reactions are classified into three groups: (a) those in which water does not participate in the rate determining step, (b) those in which water acts as a nucleophile in the rate determining step, and (c) those in which water acts as a proton transfer agent in the rate determining step.

Alternatively the linear free energy relationship proposed by Bunnett and Olsen⁷,

$$\log k_2 + H_0 = \rho(H_0 + \log C_{H^+}) + \text{constant}$$

has been applied and presented graphically (Fig. 4), the values of H_0 , have been used as reported in literature⁸.

The range of the slope ρ for different modes of involvement of water in the rate determining step were reported as, $-0.34 < \rho < 0$ for water being not involved, $0.18 < \rho < 0.47$ for water acting as a

Fig. 4. Test of the linear free energy relationship for the hydrolysis of formamide in organic solvent-water mixtures.

nucleophile and $\phi > 0.47$ for water acting as a proton transfer agent. The latter case is in agreement with our present investigation since the values of ϕ are found to be 0.74, 0.71 and 1.6 for aqueous-, *n*-propanol, isopropanol and ethylene glycol respectively, and accordingly the existence of free water molecules in systems representing the different types of behaviour is necessary to enhance the reaction rate.

The behaviour of water in the mixed solvent: Several arguments have been put forward in order to interpret the changes in the proton availability with medium composition⁹⁻¹². But experimentally it has been found that the nature and properties of the organic component may affect such proton availability. On the other hand, the solute may bring about a marked change in the state of the solvent components, since it may cause a marked increase in the activity in one of the solvent components and a marked decrease in that of the other¹³.

Experimental evidence on the behaviour of binary mixtures of simple aliphatic alcohols and water has indicated that dilute solutions of the higher alcohol homologs cause the building up of the structure of water to be enhanced¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The hydrocarbon groups in the alcohols provide sites

for the build-up of structure around the alcohol molecule; the peculiar structural features of aqueous alcohol solutions produce remarkable effects on the reaction kinetics¹⁷.

In aqueous organic solvent mixtures, activation energies, activation volumes, heat of solution¹⁸⁻²¹, internal pressure²², conductance and transference number²³ often show maxima and/or minima as the composition of the solvent changes. Accordingly we may add that the minima which have been observed in the present work; particularly in aqueous-, ethanol, *n*-propanol, and tert-butanol are due to the enhancement of the structure of water at the region of the high dielectric constant.

In case of methanol-water mixtures, the build-up of structure of water around the alcohol molecule does not occur since methanol shows about 1:1 association with water²⁴ that does not change very much even at higher alcohol concentrations where alcohol-alcohol interaction becomes important. Moreover, the interaction between the proton and the water molecule in the mixture should be stronger than in pure water, since the inductive effect of the methyl group makes the methanol molecule more basic and less acidic than the water molecule²⁵ where the negative charge on the oxygen atom is greater and the positive charge on the hydroxylic hydrogen atom is less. Cooperative hydrogen bonding transmits these characteristics also to the water molecules in the mixture. Therefore, the increasing affinity of water to the proton and the nonassociation of water molecules in methanol lead to the enhancement of the hydrolysis continuously by the successive addition of methanol.

It has been postulated that⁶ the glycol and water molecules slightly effect mutually their electron envelopes and thus no association is forthcoming. On the other hand, ethylene-glycol possess a greater acidity²⁶ than the other alcohols; this possibly arises from its capacity to form inter- and intra-molecular hydrogen bonds which increases the "B Strain" in the protonated molecule, and leads to a decrease in the electron-releasing power of the $-CH_2$ groups, resulting in a lower electron-density on both the oxygen atoms, and thus facilitating the removal of the proton; in this case the hydronium ion will predominate.

It has been expected that, the effect of ethylene glycol should be more pronounced than methyl alcohol since it is well known that glycol is more acidic than methanol. On electrostatic grounds²⁷, it was postulated that the solvation by water is greater in water-methanol rather than in water glycol.

If we can treat the polar formamide molecule as an ion, where charge separation occurs when it

reaches the activated state, then it will be preferentially solvated in aqueous glycol by the highly polar component, water, but to a lesser extent than that in methanol-water mixture.

The acid hydrolysis of formamide in aqueous isopropanol has a peculiar behaviour as compared to the hydrolysis in the other aqueous alcohols where a continuous decrease in the rate was observed even at high alcohol concentrations.

At the instant when the build-up structure of water will be gradually dispersed as the proportion of the alcohol is increased, the following equilibrium¹¹ will be established,

Due to the high basicity of isopropanol⁸ the equilibrium will be shifted almost completely to the right and the protonated species are supposed to change from $(H_2O)_n H^+$ to water solvated ROH_2^+ ions.

A mechanism was proposed^{2,8} for the acid catalysed hydrolysis of formamide which may be in agreement with the present investigation.

Considering k_3 being small in comparison with k_2 , thus,

$$\text{rate} = \frac{k_1 k_3 [\text{Amide}][H_3O^+][S]^y}{k_2 [H_2O]^x}$$

where $x = (m+n) - t$, and it represents the difference in solvation between the ground and the activated states.

In case of methanol-water and ethylene glycol-water mixtures the fraction $[H_3O^+]/[H_2O]^x$ should increase by increasing the concentration of the organic solvent component, so the rate will increase continuously, while in the case of ethanol, *n*-propanol, and tert-butanol-water mixtures the activity of the hydronium ion should pass through a minimum due to the build-up of the structure of water.

The increase in concentration of isopropanol will result in a decrease of the activity of the hydronium ion due to its high basicity compared to water. The effect of this decrease on the reaction rate is found to be more pronounced than the expected increase in rate as a result of the increase in the solvent concentration. The final result would be a continuous decrease in the rate with successive addition of isopropanol.

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